

IPAD-MD Expert Group Meeting on Data & Resources

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Meeting Report on INFRAFRONTIER Rare Diseases Data Integration Workshop

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Houston, USA

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Introduction

A rare disease (RD) is defined (by the European Commission on Public Health) as a disease afflicting fewer than one in 2000 individuals. It is estimated that 30 million people in Europe suffer from a rare disease and there are currently about 7000 rare diseases known, with more being discovered continually¹. The field of rare diseases suffers from a deficit of medical and scientific knowledge. They are also referred to as “orphan diseases”, having been orphaned by the pharmaceutical industry because of small patient populations, and consequently, a smaller drug market. Scientifically, these diseases reside in the ‘unchartered space’ of biomedical research, with their treatment marred by a dearth of medical and biochemical knowledge. Apart from being a huge emotional and financial burden to patients and their families, treatment of such rare diseases also significantly impacts public health care services and is plagued by several hidden costs².

This has led to development and implementation of several strategies to tackle the treatment of rare and debilitating diseases. For example, the European Commission supports rare disease research through Horizon 2020 (<https://ec.europa.eu/research/health/index.cfm?pg=area&areaname=rare>) with €900 million available to more than 160 collaborative projects related to rare diseases.

The core services of INFRAFRONTIER comprise the systemic phenotyping of mouse mutants in the participating mouse clinics, and the archiving and distribution of mouse mutant lines by the European Mouse Mutant Archive (EMMA). INFRAFRONTIER aids in rare disease research by providing access to 670 mouse strains (via EMMA) that are related to nearly 1200 distinct rare diseases. These mouse strains carry mutations in genes that are

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/health/non_communicable_diseases/rare_diseases_en

² Genetic Alliance UK, The Hidden Costs Of Rare Diseases, https://www.geneticalliance.org.uk/media/2502/hidden-costs-full-report_21916-v2-1.pdf

implicated in causing rare diseases (<https://www.infrafrontier.eu/infrafrontier-and-rare-diseases>).

However, there is a dire need for close engagement among human geneticists, rare disease clinicians and mouse researchers. This multi-directional interaction will enable human geneticists to find appropriate mouse models for their rare disease research in the mouse research community. In turn, mouse researchers can generate rare disease models with specific disease-causing mutations found in human patients in the orthologous mouse gene. These interactions will facilitate diagnosis and treatment.

The Rare Disease Data Integration (RDDI) workshop, funded by the IPAD-MD project (grant agreement No. 653961), intended to meet these needs. The main aims of the workshop were:

- Align relevant genetic and phenotypic data from model organisms with rare diseases clinical data.
- Develop communication channels between rare disease clinicians and mouse geneticists to facilitate a bilateral exchange of resources and information.
- Explore making custom mouse models for rare disease consortia and showcase the available lines among the mouse research community.
- Bring together mouse geneticists, global rare disease communities, human geneticists and clinicians to facilitate the understanding and treatment of rare diseases.

The workshop included participants from leading human genetics projects and mouse resources like:

- **RD-Connect** – an integrated platform for rare disease research that connects databases, registries, biobanks and clinical bioinformatics.
- **The European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases (EJP-RD)** – a 5-year programme co-funded by the European Commission to create a comprehensive and sustainable ecosystem for rare disease (RD) research.

- **EMBL-EBI** – the European Bioinformatics Institute that helps maintain the IMPC’s data portal.
- **Centers for Mendelian Genomics** – Centers that are funded by the National Human Genome Research Institute (NHGRI) for the discovery of the genetic basis of Mendelian disorders.
- **Gabriella Miller Kids First Pediatric Research Program (Kids First)** – a NIH Common Funds funded project to investigate the biology of childhood cancer and structural birth defects.
- **Monarch Initiative** – a bioinformatics web resource focused on connecting genotypes with phenotypes to combat genetic diseases.

INFRAFRONTIER Rare Diseases Data Integration Workshop at ASHG 2019, Hilton Americas-Houston

Workshop details

Date and Time

15th October, 08:30 – 13:30

Venue

Hilton Americas-Houston

Room 336, Level 3

Agenda

	Registration	08:30	09:00
<i>Asrar Ali Khan</i>	Welcome and Introduction	09:00	09:10
<i>Michael Raess</i>	INFRAFRONTIER Resources for Rare Diseases Research	09:10	09:25
<i>Peter Robinson</i>	Exomiser: Leveraging Model Data for Gene Discovery and Diagnostics	09:25	09:40
<i>Allison Heath</i>	Gabriella Miller Kids First Data Resource Center: Collaborative Platforms for Accelerating Cross-Disease Pediatric Research Across Development and Cancer	09:40	09:55
	Coffee Break	09:55	10:25
<i>Damian Smedley</i>	Use of Animal Models in the 100,000 Genomes Project	10:25	10:40
<i>Shinya Yamamoto</i>	Informatics Analysis in the UDN MOSC to Prioritize Candidate Genes and Variants	10:40	10:55
<i>Sergi Beltran</i>	RD-Connect and the European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases	10:55	11:10
<i>Violeta Munoz-Fuentes / Robert Wilson</i>	IMPC – Integrating Mouse Models with Rare Disease Clinical Data	11:10	11:25
	Group Discussion	11:25	12:25
	Lunch	12:25	13:25

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Workshop Overview

Welcome and Introduction

Dr. Asrar Ali Khan, INFRAFRONTIER GmbH

Dr. Ali Khan started by giving the welcome address with a brief introduction of the INFRAFRONTIER Research Infrastructure. The RDDI workshop idea came about in the panel discussion at the INFRAFRONTIER Stakeholder Meeting 2018 Munich (refer to deliverable D2.4). During the panel discussion the need for a follow-up expert group meeting for data integration between model organism resources and rare disease clinical data was brought forward. The objectives and the agenda of the workshop were presented followed by expected outcomes of the workshop aimed towards the following groups:

a) Mouse researchers - how to better present information on data portals in order to communicate available mouse resources to human clinicians

(e.g., available transgenic mice and specialised phenotyping services).

b) Human geneticists:

- What are the expectations from an animal model resource?
- How can be clinical information be communicated to mouse geneticists:
 - Custom alleles and point mutations
 - Human phenotype data
- How can patient identity be concealed and medical data securely exchanged?
- How can mouse resource centers effectively present mouse model data back to the clinical researchers?

INFRAFRONTIER Resources for Rare Diseases Research

Dr. Michael Raess, INFRAFRONTIER GmbH

Dr. Raess explained the concept of a European Research Infrastructure to the audience followed by an introduction of INFRAFRONTIER that expanded Dr. Ali Khan's part. Dr. Raess highlighted some of INFRAFRONTIER core services:

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- Model development: precision mammalian models that include mouse and rat.
- Systemic phenotyping: comprehensive phenotypic analysis of mouse mutants in the INFRAFRONTIER mouse clinics.
- Archiving and distribution: more than 7200 unique mouse strains archived and distributed by the European Mouse Mutant Archive (EMMA).

These services contribute large specialized data sets that include:

- Genetic data of mouse strains
- Phenotypic descriptions of mouse strains
- Disease associations
- Characterization protocols
- Breeding and animal welfare
- Publications
- Ownership
- Distribution/shipping logistics

Other forms of data integration also occur, for example, with the Mouse Genome Informatics resource for standardised genetic nomenclature, gene and allele IDs, etc. These points led to an INFRAFRONTIER data integration use case for rare diseases – the INFRAFRONTIER and Rare Diseases page (<https://www.infrafrontier.eu/infrafrontier-and-rare-diseases>) that allows researchers to find mouse strains related to rare diseases linked with Orphanet (<https://www.orpha.net/consor/cgi-bin/index.php>) identifiers. INFRAFRONTIER's next steps towards rare diseases data integration include making EMMA strains easily findable to Rare Disease researchers, expose INFRAFRONTIER RD expert partners to RD researchers and make RD researchers aware of the entire portfolio of INFRAFRONTIER services.

Exomiser: Leveraging Model Data for Gene Discovery and Diagnostics

Prof. Dr. Peter Robinson, Monarch Initiative / The Jackson Laboratory

Prof. Robinson started his talk with the importance of ontology for precision medicine. This led into his work on the Human Phenotype Ontology (<https://hpo.jax.org>) that uses a fuzzy phenotyping matching algorithm and is used by different research groups to make differential diagnoses and search for novel disease genes. An example of this ‘precision fuzzy phenotype matching’ was briefly presented, with patients with different gene variants in the same gene leading in the same disease (Wiedemann Steiner syndrome)³. The importance of extending the range of phenotyping analysis by cross-species annotations and linking human diseases to animal models was presented in the case of *PAX6*⁴. An example of cross-species phenotype comparisons for a priority gene from the Undiagnosed Disease Network was also presented. The segued into Exomiser – a bioinformatics tool that combines genetic (exome sequencing) and phenotypic data (humans and animal models) to prioritise pathogenic gene variants (Figure 1).

³ Zemojtel et al., Science Translational Medicine, 03 Sep 2014: Vol. 6, Issue 252, pp. 252ra123

⁴ Washington et al., PLOS Biology, 24 November 2009, 7(11): e1000247.

Exomiser: Combining G & P data for variant prioritization

Figure 1: Exomiser – Combining genetic and phenotypic data for variant prioritization

Prof. Peterson showcased an example of how Exomiser solved a novel rare disease case that involved platelet abnormalities, novel heterozygous missense mutations in *STIM-1* and an MGI-curated mouse model. Lastly, the Monarch Initiative uses HPO to curate and harmonise disease definitions – phenotypic features, genetic variation and environmental factors and integrate biological information using semantics, and present it in a novel way.

Gabriella Miller Kids First Data Resource Center: Collaborative platforms for accelerating cross-disease pediatric research across development and cancer

Dr. Allison Heath, Children’s Hospital of Philadelphia

Dr. Heath is the lead developer of the Gabriella Miller Kids First Data Research Center (DRC).

The Gabriella Miller Kids First Pediatric Research Program (Kids First,

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<https://commonfund.nih.gov/kidsfirst>) was launched in 2015 to develop a large-scale data resource to help researchers uncover new insights into the biology of childhood cancer and structural birth defects, including the discovery of shared genetic pathways between these disorders by integrating dispersed data from different sources into one location and providing support for analyses. In 2018, the Gabriella Miller Kids DRC established the Gabriella Miller Kids First Data Resource Portal, a large-scale database of clinical and genetic data from patients with childhood cancers and structural birth defects and their families. The main objective of the DRC is to develop data-driven platforms that integrate large amounts of clinical and genomic data from a variety of disease types empowering collaborative discoveries – a virtual workspace where researchers can work together across different domains.

In the first 4 years (since 2015), 26 projects have been funded via the Kids First X01 grants that analysed about 10,000 patients (including family members and tumors) with 8 datasets released. The latest X01 grant is focussed towards genetic syndromes like structural brain defects and aims to sequence 10,000 genomes. Dr. Heath stressed that one of the main ways the DRC supports research projects is by enabling interoperability across relevant datasets, resources and applications within the emerging NIH “Commons” landscape, for example, intersecting the Undiagnosed Disease Network (UDN) data with Kids First data sets. The DRC also focuses heavily on having their datasets curated with community engagement for additions and/or recommendations.

Dr. Heath also presented the use of mouse models by Kids First in a pilot project together with KOMP2 that develops mouse strains to study, phenotype, and validate coding and noncoding genetic variants (e.g. missense, structural variants, copy number variants, INDELS, frame shifts) identified from Kids First datasets (<https://commonfund.nih.gov/kidsfirst/collaboration>).

Dr. Heath ended her presentation with a demo of the aforementioned Data Resource Portal (<https://portal.kidsfirstdrc.org/>) that showcased the portal dashboard management, cohort builder that navigates different interoperable and collaborative data sets in real time, the search functionality with aortic defects as an example, duplication and overlapping of data sets and launching a demo project in Cavatica (a cloud-based workspace).

Use of Animal Models in the 100,000 Genomes Project

Damian Smedley, Queen Mary University of London

Dr. Smedley introduced the 100,000 Genomes Project that was established to sequence 100,000 genomes of NHS patients affected by a rare disease or cancer. So far 116,268 genomes have been sequenced, representing around 85,000 patients and their relatives, with 20-25% actionable findings for rare diseases and about 50% cancer cases with potential for a therapy or a trial in the latest report. Their main bioinformatics pipeline (Figure 2), used from the start, is based on identifying rare, protein-altering variants that segregate within the family and predict a MOI for that gene if it's a known disease gene. A virtual panel-based approach is used based on one or more expert-curated panels that have been assigned to each family and on their recruited disease category and additional clinical data. Loss-of-function (LOF) and de novo variants affecting a gene in the applied panel are classified as tier 1, missense variants as tier 2 and those affecting genes outside the panels as tier 3. The idea here is to prioritise a small number of tier 1 and 2 variants affecting genes in the applied panels for initial review by the clinical geneticists, but they are also presented with the whole genome to allow diagnoses outside the panels or even those that have been filtered out.

Variant filtering/prioritisation

Figure 2: Genomics England’s main bioinformatics pipeline for variant prioritisation.

Linking back to Prof. Robinson’s talk, Dr. Smedley presented Exomiser as a part of the ISO accredited Genomics England pipeline with results presented back to NHS. Dr. Smedley ended his talk with two examples of new variants discovered using burden testing analysis, i.e., enrichment of certain types of variants (like loss-of-function) in cases vs. controls and the use of precision mouse models for validation via the Genome Editing Mice for Medicine (GEMM) program. To date, under GEMM 300 mouse lines have been nominated by the UK biomedical community with 89 selected for production and 40 lines have already been delivered that include point mutation, regulatory region deletions, cell-specific Cre line and humanised allele in various disciplines like neuroscience, rare diseases and cancer.

Informatics analysis in the UDN MOSC to prioritize candidate genes and variants

Dr. Shinya Yamamoto, Baylor College of Medicine

Dr. Yamamoto is the co-director of the Drosophila Core at the Model Organisms Screening Center (MOSC) for the Undiagnosed Diseases Network (UDN) and introduced the overall

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workflow of the UDN and MOSC (Figure 3) that involves rare disease patients, the UDN coordinating center, metabolic and sequencing cores and the MOSC.

Figure 3: The workflow of the UDN and MOSC⁵

As a use case of rare disease data integration between clinical and model organism data, Dr. Yamamoto presented the MARRVEL (Model organism Aggregated Resources for Rare Variant ExpLoration, <http://marrvel.org>) informatics analysis process using an example from the UDN. This example was a pediatric patient (22 months, male) from the Vanderbilt clinical site that exhibited developmental delay, dysmorphic features (prominent forehead, malformed jaw), macrocephaly, hydrocephalus, sensory neural hearing loss, nystagmus and bilateral clubfoot. Using MARRVEL, 4 candidate genes provided by the clinic from their trio-WES/WGS analysis were investigated. The gene-phenotype relationships (from OMIM), reported alleles (from OMIM) and control population gene summary were looked at for the candidate genes along with variants that affect conserved amino acids and animal models, if available. In the end, this affliction called Saul-Wilson Syndrome was caused by a specific heterozygous *COG4* substitution⁶. This was validated using *cog4* zebrafish mutants (loss of function) that exhibited craniofacial, ear and fin defects as well as jaw and bone defects that were similar to human patients.

⁵ Wangler et al., Genetics, September 2017, DOI: 10.1534/genetics.117.203067

⁶ Ferreira et al., Am J Hum Genet. 2018 Oct 4;103(4):553-567. doi: 10.1016/j.ajhg.2018.09.003.

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RD-Connect and the European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases

Dr. Sergi Beltran, CNAG-CRG

Dr. Sergi Beltran is the head of the Bioinformatics Analysis Unit at the CNAG-CRG and leads the development of the RD-Connect Genome-Phenome Analysis Platform (GPAP). Dr. Beltran started his talk with a slide on the impact of reaching an accurate and timely molecular diagnosis, which includes more treatment options (curative, preventive), genetic counselling, reduced patient and family anxiety and reduced healthcare costs. This segued into the RD-Connect Genome-Phenome Analysis Platform (GPAP, platform.rd-connect.eu), a platform where sequence data submitted by participating research projects is processed with a standard pipeline and made available for online analysis through a user-friendly interface to authorised users (Figure 4).

Figure 4: the RD-Connect Genome-Phenome Analysis Platform (GPAP, platform.rd-connect.eu)

Dr. Beltran proceeded to present and explain the GPAP interface that included the different filters applicable, how to add specific patient information from the underlying databases and the output list of genetic variants. Additional functionalities of GPAP like standard filters and annotations for SNVs, InDels and CNVs (variant impact on protein,

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frequency in control populations, frequency within database, in silico predictors, gene, genomic position, etc.), filter by genes of interest (predefined/custom lists, GEL's PanelApp, Mendelian.co, OMIM disease, HPO symptoms or Reactome), phenotype driven strategy for variant prioritization (Exomiser), filter by variants annotated in ClinVar database, etc. were also explained. Dr. Beltran ended his talk with a project layout overview of the Solve-RD project, a research project funded by the European Commission for five years (2018-2022) that echoes the ambitious goals set out by the International Rare Diseases Research Consortium (IRDiRC) to deliver diagnostic tests for most rare diseases by 2020, and also introduced the European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases (EJP-RD, grant agreement No. 825575). EJP-RD's objectives, structure and consortium network were also presented.

IMPC – Integrating mouse models with rare disease clinical data

Dr. Violeta Munoz-Fuentes / Dr. Robert Wilson, EMBL-EBI

Dr. Munoz-Fuentes started the presentation introducing IMPC's goals and some of the key IMPC findings that included demonstrated extensive pleiotropy and sexual dimorphism and semantic phenotype overlap of mouse strains and human diseases, as well as systematic analyses published on metabolism, hearing, eyesight, etc. based on mouse knockout strains. With over 1,500 CRISPR-modified lines, IMPC offers a valuable insight into mammalian genome editing enhancing precision medicine research. Dr. Munoz-Fuentes also provided an update for an upcoming IMPC publication that measures how essential a gene is in supporting life, inferred from the overlap between IMPC screens and human cell line essentiality screens. A novel cross-species gene classification was proposed across the Full Spectrum of Intolerance to Loss-of-function (FUSIL) that categorized genes into five mutually exclusive FUSIL categories with differing characteristics in the biological processes they regulate, tissue expression levels and human mutation rates. The study observed that the developmental lethal category is enriched for genes associated with developmental disease along with the identification of 163 novel candidate genes for developmental diseases. An

example from the publication was also presented with strong phenotype and genetic evidence from a human patient that was pheno-copied in an IMPC knock-out mouse strain.

The talk also highlighted several challenges in aligning animal models with rare disease data:

- Allele design (humanized genes, orthologues)
- Continue connecting clinical phenotype data with mouse phenotypes
- Coordinate mouse production across rare disease consortia
- Tracking system to accommodate all types of planned induced mutations
- Finding best ways to provide feedback / communicate design, production, phenotyping results

Dr. Wilson reported on a new mouse production tracking system called GenTaR (Genome Targeting Repository) that the team at EMBL-EBI are currently working on to fulfil the requirements needed for tracking planned mouse models with precise mutations. This new system will replace iMITS (<https://www.mousephenotype.org/imits/>) – the current IMPC tracking tool. The reasons for a new system are a CRISPR paradigm shift, precision medicine models based on human variants and haplo-essential gene projects that track individually targeted embryos. Dr. Wilson also explained the new infrastructure underlying this system along with the database overview that will consist of three main components – organisation (user identity, affiliation and association with different consortia and production centers etc.), project (allele intention, phenotyping plan etc.) and reference data (reference human genes, orthologues etc.). The project workflow for GenTaR can consist of multiple production and phenotyping plans along with configurable and flexible user permission and data privacy options. This feature is a solution to the data security concerns regarding the sharing of patient data. Three levels of data access policy settings can be selected – public, protected and restricted. Data access depends on the user and the privacy settings of the project and all data will become publicly available following an embargo period. In addition, users can have different roles. The presentation ended with a screenshot of list of genes that was requested by the Centers for Mendelian Genetics (CMG). GenTaR is not currently open, a prototype will be demonstrated at the IMPC Fall Meeting 2019 in Maryland.

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Discussion Overview and Outcome

The workshop involved participants from prominent human genetics projects like 100,000 Genomes Project, Kids First and CMG (in the audience); rare disease networks and projects like the UDN and RD-Connect; mouse repositories and research infrastructures like IMPC and INFRAFRONTIER / EMMA and; large scale online bioinformatics resources for genetic diseases like the Monarch Initiative. With this diverse and comprehensive participation, the workshop garnered meaningful interactions between human geneticists, mouse researchers and bioinformatics specialists. The group discussion at the end of the workshop offered several ideas and suggestions on how data integration can be improved. The discussion can be summarised in the following points:

- It was recommended to have more hands-on workshops at human genetics conferences organised by mouse research projects and infrastructures. The focus of these workshops should be how the mouse bioinformatics and repository resources can be used by human geneticists.
- Future workshops involving disease areas like rare diseases should also include patient organisations; e.g., EURORDIS would be a potential attendee in the rare disease field.
- The mouse repositories and resources should be better linked to one another allowing new users to find their desired mouse strains or phenotypic data in different mouse archives and repositories.
- A data portal or an interface for existing data portals intended for patients and non-scientists was also suggested. This will help patients interested in learning more about their disease / gene variant. An example of this is the Matchmaker Exchange for patients (https://www.matchmakerexchange.org/i_am_a_patient.html) that supports patient-led matching as well as individuals and families to share genetic and health information to identify other individuals with similar profiles.
- It is important to ensure that the genetic data from these projects is interoperable, i.e., it can be used by other scientific communities using different vocabularies. This

is an important aspect to consider for data integration between human and mouse genetic data.

- The idea of registering interest or nominating gene / variant to the mouse community was brought up several times. This nomination can be coupled to relevant detailed phenotypes and/or scientific question being investigated. This would be useful to researchers that require a specific mouse strain and are not part of a large consortium or research infrastructure. IMPC and MMRRC have this feature, however, it was suggested to make this a more prominent feature of the webpage (as a 'big banner').
- However, opening up avenues for gene / variant nominations can increase the noise in the system, i.e., nominations that might not be pathogenically relevant. This is a concern as generation of precision mouse models is expensive and time consuming. It was suggested that a free-text box, stating reasons for interest, could be included. A curation team would be required to process the nominations. A consensus for nominations or the number of nominations for a particular gene or variant is also a solution that is being employed by the MMRRC. The quality of variants is an issue for some centers like the UDN MOSC.
- In addition, the 'Contact Us' feature at the IMPC website should also be made prominent, focusing on very short response times to queries. The analogy to going next door and asking mouse researcher colleagues personally was made to the implementation of this feature.
- It was also suggested to make mouse strains on EMMA findable using Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO) terms.

The following outcomes are planned with regard to the above-mentioned discussion points:

- Involvement in human genetics conferences – INFRAFRONTIER will be present at the RE(ACT) Congress 2020 and the European Human Genetics Conference 2020 in Berlin with INFRAFRONTIER booth and posters.
- Links to other mouse services, inclusion of searchable HPO terms and register interest – these aspects have been noted for the implementation of new interfaces for the EMMA database in the future.

- A prominent 'Contact Us' functionality – This aspect will be considered for the upcoming INFRAFRONTIER website revamp.
- Initial data integration with rare disease projects – An API will be provided to RD-Connect that will enable the inclusion of EMMA strain data into GPAP.